

Sarbanes Oxley Act

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Introduction

At the beginning of twenty first century, capital market of United States of America was derailed by disclosure of accounting and financial scandals at various international and national companies of the country (Coates, 2007). The outcome of these scandals was hilarious for citizens and it resulted in punishment for various corporate citizens. Moreover, these scandals became the bases of the disclosure of various companies that resulted in severe loss in financial terms.

In light of these scandals and decline in the faith of public over integrity and value of financial reporting, US senate and government official supported implementation of Sarbanes-Oxley Act and it was officially incorporated in US law in year 2002. Since its incorporation the SOX, has been equally appreciated and criticized and according to Ernst and young it is significant to think about the purpose behind the development of this act and to re-examine the overall affect of its implementation.

Sarbanes Oxley Act was created to improve the authenticity and accuracy of financial reporting and to enhance the overall quality of auditing of these reports (Engel et al, 2007). According to Ernst & Young the act has able to restore the faith of public over financial reporting, however, it still needs to reform on continual bases. There is no denying the fact that SOX initiated a new period for audit profession in USA by dismantling traditional procedure of self-regulation in public companies and establishing self-governing oversight of public company audits by (PCOAB) Public Company Accounting Oversight Board.

SOX in public companies reinforced and improved the structure of corporate governance, shifted audit responsibilities from corporate management to self-governing audit committees (Fairfax, 2002). It introduced the concept of whistleblower programs, severe

punishments for all kinds of mismanagement and illegal activities, and other program with the only objective of ensuring fair and accurate reporting of financial information to investors, shareholders, and other important members of the organization.

Discussion

Audit committees of public company boards of directors

Sarbanes-Oxley's introduced (PCAOB) that finished traditional self-regulation at corporate level by audit professional of public companies is viewed as the extraordinary impact of SOX implementation. In current era, it is the responsibility of PCOAB to manage audit companies, regulate and define rules and principles of auditing, frequently monitor the quality of audit, conduct detail investigation on reports of mismanagement, and others. Until December

2012, more than 2300 audit companies from around 80 countries of the globe has registered with PCAOB and in year 2012 the PCOAB board carried out scrutiny of 213 audit firms that are registered with the board, and started an short-term evaluation curriculum for broker-dealers(Gordon, 2002). Regulation and principles set by PCAOB play a vital role in enhancing the overall quality of the audit and ensure sovereignty of auditors providing comprehensive benefits to investors.

Inspections

Examination procedure of PCAOB is an important aspect of its efforts to ensure quality of audit and fair representation of financial reporting. Management of Ernst and young is of the view that yearly examination provides them with the opportunity of identifying the gaps in audit and rectifies those elements. Since its incorporation, the PCOAB has examined various registered audit firms at different time, particularly based on total

quantity of public companies audited by these firms(Langevoort, D005). According to its standard principles, (PCAOB) has identified a quantifiable scale for the examination of audit firms which is generally based on numbers of firms audited by a audit firm during a particular period.

For examination PCAOB prefers to use diversified tools for the identification of specific aspect of audit firms, however, according to reports it prefers to monitor the risk present in the financial reports of public company and various other elements which allows them the opportunity of analyzing the quality of audit conducted and identify possible scope for enhancement in audit reports. This procedure is conducted at both audit firm and public company audited by that firm and outcome of its evaluation tend to classify elements that might require supervision, training to auditors for improving their skills that would ultimately lead to improvement in auditor performance and improvement in quality of audit reports.

Enforcement

In light of its mission of improving the quality of audit report, the PCAOB has developed a team of enforcement staff that is responsible for examining and punishing auditors and audit companies if found violating the rules and regulation set by the PCAOB.

Enhanced auditor independence

This act has ensured autonomy of auditor and identified various categories of non-audit services as unnecessary for audit companies that are providing their services to public companies of the country(Litvak, 2007). Moreover, it is the responsibility of public company autonomous audit committee approves extra services executed by external auditor.

Strengthened CEO's and CFO's of public companies

A unique step that drastically reinforced corporate governance, instructed CEO's and CFO to concentrate on the major aspects of business operations and removed them from the responsibilities of audit that were assigned to audit committees. Moreover, it instructed the boards of public limited companies that are listed in stock exchange to develop audit committees that would only comprises of board members that are not part of company management because according to the principles of SOX committees would be responsible for selecting, evaluating, compensating the work of external auditor.

The selected external auditor of the company would be solely responsible for analyzing the financial reports generated by the company are in accordance with the standard set by SOX and are presented in fair, accurate, and reliable manner(Ribstein, 2003). In order to improve the quality of financial reporting, SOX has instructed every public limited company form audit committee and has made certain changes in the principles of security exchange commission and US stock exchange. With circulation of new rules, various companies were forced to restructure their audit committees and this resulted in criticism from various corners.

In addition to this, company must introduce innovative communication procedure to ensure proper and timely communication between audit committee and external auditor that would generally include following important discussion.

- Accounting principles used by company for the development of financial reports
- Alternative accounting principles discussed by the management, and advantages and disadvantages of changing accounting principles
- Revelation of other important details of the financial reports

Enhanced transparency, executive accountability and investor protection

The primary responsibility of Sarbanes-Oxley act was to precisely explain and distribute liability of developing financial statements among company chief financial officer and chief executive officer and instructed both these individual to verify various item between each other for every annual, quarterly reports of the company.

- Both these personals have reviewed the report
- According to their knowledge and experience financial information enclosed in reports are fair and accurate
- According to this knowledge, financial reports does not include any sort of misinterpreted information, nor any important information has been deleted from the report which could raise concerns over the authenticity of the report.
- Both CFO and CEO have accepted their liability for developing and maintaining proper internal control on company financial reporting and other important revelation
- These personal have examined the efficiency of internal control, provided the outcome to the best of their efficiency, and revealed any deliberate or proper changes in accounts of the company by keeping themselves accountable for company's financial reports.

Conclusion

There is no denying the fact that SOX has able to bring comprehensive changes and enhancement in audit procedure and their independence, but to ensure continuity and stability in audit procedure for long period the members of parliament and concern authority needs to made frequent and relevant changes in SOX standards and principles. In addition to this, it is the responsibility of public company to adopt and implement an effective communication

structure for proper and timely communication between all the members of auditing procedure.

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